

Supplementary Information:

BioQuantum Record: Exploring otherness through extremophilic microorganisms

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Mirror Life – Testing Enzymatic Boundaries

Mirror Life and Chiral Handshake

A scientific question has arisen from an artistic narrative: Can our microbial astronauts carry the proposed sweet chiral gifts to their extra-terrestrial counterparts? Or will they “eat” it during their long interstellar travel, which would be inappropriate, impolite, and diplomatically incorrect? In biomolecules such as amino acids and sugars, chirality arises from the presence of at least one carbon atom that engages in covalent bonds with four different substituents, giving rise to two possible forms, called enantiomers, which are chirally inverted “mirror images” in three dimensions (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: A tetrahedral carbon atom (“C”) with four different substituents, S₁, S₂, S₃, and S₄ (e.g., different groups of atoms), can exist in two different “enantiomeric” chirally inverted forms.

25 *A Chiral Gift – Testing Enzymatic Boundaries*

26 Enzymes are proteins, *i.e.*, macromolecules composed of hundreds of homochiral
27 amino acids linked together and then “folded” into a compact chiral three-dimensional
28 structure capable of recognizing and binding to a “substrate” molecule and catalyzing
29 its transformation into one or several “product” molecules. If the substrate is chiral,
30 the (chiral) enzyme does not operate equally on both its native substrate and its
31 chirally inverted version, such as a left-hand glove that does not fit a right hand. An
32 enzyme selectively interacts with a particular spatial arrangement of atoms in its
33 substrate, typically one enantiomer, while showing little or no activity toward its mirror
34 image (Brik and Wong 2003). This selectivity arises from the three-dimensional
35 complementarity between the active site of the enzyme and the specific configuration
36 of its substrate. As such, even subtle changes (*e.g.*, chirality inversion) can
37 completely abolish binding or catalysis. In biological systems, where molecular
38 recognition and function critically depend on stereochemistry, a chirally inverted
39 substrate is, in most cases, effectively invisible to the enzyme.

40 In the framework of our art and science project, we focus on enzymes acting on
41 “sugars”, also known as carbohydrates, which are biomolecules typically composed
42 of multiple chiral carbon atoms, each linked to an oxygen atom. Among sugars, in
43 addition to the pentoses (5 carbon atoms) D -2-deoxy-ribose and D -ribose, which are
44 the core chiral parts of DNA and RNA, respectively, the hexose family (6 carbons, 6
45 oxygens) is the most abundant and includes D -glucose, a crucial source of energy in
46 all organisms on Earth, which is used as a starting substrate for metabolic pathways
47 consisting of cascades of different enzymes. Although the enzymes and reactions
48 they catalyze differ substantially depending on the type of organism, the starting
49 substrate is always conserved: D -glucose.

50 One would expect an extra-terrestrial form of life to also use glucose as an energy
51 source. Five of the six carbons in glucose are chiral, and other hexoses in which the
52 chirality of one or several carbons is inverted (so-called “diastereoisomers”) play
53 important biological roles. For example, galactose is the carbon 4 (C4)
54 diastereoisomer, mannose is the C1 diastereoisomer, and talose is the C1/C4
55 (**Figure 2**). A distinctive feature of glucose compared to other hexoses is its ability to
56 adopt a “chair-like” three-dimensional shape (chemists call that a “conformation”), in
57 which the ring core, composed of five carbon and one oxygen atoms, positions its
58 substituents predominantly in equatorial orientations (*i.e.*, lying in the plane defined
59 by the chair). This arrangement makes glucose relatively flat and exceptionally
60 stable, as the bulky oxygen atoms are quite far from each other, avoiding spatial
61 conflicts (“steric clashes”). Such an “all-equatorial” configuration is thought to have
62 been favored by evolution on Earth, making glucose the preferred fuel for life on
63 Earth.

64

65 **Figure 2:** Schematic three-dimensional shapes (conformations) of selected hexoses. The
 66 compounds shown are D-glucose, D-galactose, D-talose, D-mannose, and the enantiomer L-
 67 glucose. Each six-atom ring (“pyranose”) adopts a chair conformation, highlighting the
 68 differences in the orientation of the hydroxyl groups (axial vs. equatorial) that distinguish the
 69 stereoisomers. In the case of L-galactose, L-mannose, or L-talose, only one or two
 70 substituents are axial, and the chair has the same orientation as L-glucose. In the case of D-
 71 glucose, rotation of the bonds causes it to adopt an inverted chair conformation.

72 Thus, one could imagine that L-glucose, the enantiomer of glucose in which all five
 73 chiral carbons are inverted, could have been selected by homochirality-divergent
 74 earth-independent forms of life as a source of energy because, as a mirror image, it
 75 shares all the stability features of D-glucose, as detailed earlier. L-glucose does not
 76 occur naturally in earth-borne living organisms but can be synthesized in the
 77 laboratory. It adopts an “inverted chair” three-dimensional structure, which is a mirror
 78 image of D-glucose (see **Figure 2**).

79 In its isolated form, glucose carbon #1 (C1) displays a hydroxyl (-OH) group (in
 80 addition to those at C2, C3, C4, and C6) that can rapidly interconvert between two
 81 chiral configurations, namely α and β (**Figure 3**); however, the C1 hydroxyl group can
 82 also form a covalent bond with another molecule, affording “glycosides” (the
 83 hydrogen atom, H, is replaced by another, typically a carbon). As a glycoside, the C1
 84 carbon of glucose is locked in a fixed configuration, either α or β .

85

86 **Figure 3:** Isolated form of D -glucose, in which the interconversion between its α and β C1
 87 configurations is allowed, versus the glycoside form of D -glucose, in which the C1 chiral
 88 configurations are locked.

89 Many organisms store glucose in polymeric forms, such as glycogen in animals and
 90 starch in plants, which can be depolymerized by enzymes on demand to release
 91 “free” isolated glucose, which is then used as an energy source. Besides its role in
 92 energy storage, cellulose—a glucose polymer composed of linear chains of several
 93 hundred to many thousands of β - D -glucose units (**Figure 4**)—is a crucial structural
 94 component of plant cell walls, which gives plants strength and rigidity, and is the
 95 most abundant organic polymer on Earth: terrestrial plants globally produce ~ 100
 96 billion tonnes of cellulose every year.

97

98 **Figure 4:** Molecular structure of cellulose.

99 We focused on β -glucosidases, enzymes that catalyze the breakage of the β -
 100 glucosidic bond via the addition of a water molecule (hydrolysis). Although mammals
 101 do not produce β -glucosidase enzymes to digest cellulose, they do express certain β -
 102 glucosidases for breaking down specific glucosides. However, many microorganisms,
 103 including archaea, bacteria (particularly ruminant gut microbiomes), fungi, and

104 yeasts, express and secrete these enzymes. In our experiment, we investigated
105 whether the enzymes of our chosen microorganism could hydrolyze the β -glucosidic
106 bond in a D-glucoside “molecular probe” compared to an L-glucoside probe. We did
107 not anticipate that Earth-borne enzymes would hydrolyze the mirror-image substrate¹
108 and aimed to obtain visual feedback on its selectivity. In principle, the mirror-image
109 substrate could only be efficiently hydrolyzed by an “alien” mirror-image glycosidase,
110 thereby serving as precursors of our intended sweet “chiral gift”, L-glucose. Our
111 synthetic sugar probes are chromogenic substrates (*p*-nitrophenyl glucosides) that
112 release a bright yellow compound (*p*-nitrophenolate) upon hydrolysis (**Figure 5**).

113

114 **Figure 5:** Enzymatic hydrolysis of para-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucopyranoside (*p*NPG) releases
115 bright yellow para-nitrophenolate, whereas the enzyme activity is expected to be null with
116 respect to the *L-p*NPG substrate, which is the mirror-image version of *p*NPG.

117 The resulting color change provides a straightforward visual signal that can be easily
118 measured; for this reason, these probes are commonly used in laboratory assays to
119 monitor enzyme activity. *p*NPG is commercially available and has been extensively
120 used as a probe to quantify the catalytic efficiency of a purified β -glucosidase
121 enzyme (Riou et al. 1998; Lin et al. 2010) or to detect β -glucosidase secretion by
122 microorganisms such as fungi (Madhu et al. 2009), bacteria (Strahsburger et al.
123 2017), and yeasts (Liu et al. 2020). To our knowledge, no attempts have been made
124 to monitor β -glucosidase secretion by archaea, although the presence of β -
125 glucosidase has been evidenced (Schröder et al. 2014).

¹ A few microbial enzymes with L-glucosidase activity have been reported. For example, studies have described L-fucosidases and L-rhamnosidases with very weak ability to act on L-glucose linkages, which is considered as promiscuous” catalytic activity, not selected by evolution.

126 **Materials and Methods**

127 *Microbial Cultivation*

128 *Metallosphaera sedula* DSM 5348 was grown aerobically in DSMZ 88 medium with
129 pyrite, as previously described by Gfellner et al. (2025) in 1 L glassblower modified
130 Schott-bottle bioreactors (Duran DWK Life Sciences GmbH, Wertheim/ Main,
131 Germany). The stock culture was stored at -80°C in a solution containing equal parts
132 of 50% glycerol and DSMZ 88 medium (50, 50, v:v). The DSMZ 88 medium
133 contained 9.84 mM $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 2.06 mM KH_2PO_4 , 1.01 mM $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.48 mM
134 $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 0.07 mM $\text{FeCl}_3 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and it also served as the medium for cell
135 resuspension. Additionally, Allen trace element solution was added, which contained
136 0.91 mM $\text{MnCl}_2 \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.18 mM $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \times 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.08 mM $\text{ZnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.03
137 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01 mM $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.02 mM $\text{VOSO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 3.56
138 μM $\text{CoSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. As previously described by Kölbl et al. (2017), 0.1% tryptone was
139 added to the DSMZ 88 medium. The pH was set to 2.0 using 5 M H_2SO_4 . Pyrite was
140 manually crushed with a hand grinder to achieve particle sizes between 63–100 μm ,
141 regulated by 63 and 100 μm mesh sieves, and then baked overnight at 180°C . Pyrite
142 at a concentration of 10 g/L was added to 800 mL of culture. A 1 L bioreactor was
143 assembled, maintained at a constant temperature of 73°C , and continuously stirred.
144 A CO_2 flow at a total rate of 0.9 L/min (normalized to 1 atm and 0°C) was maintained
145 for the interconnected triplicate bioreactor setup, resulting in a flow rate of 0.3 L/min
146 for each bioreactor.

147 To track microbial growth, samples from the cultures were collected continuously
148 throughout the growth phase, and cell counts were determined using a microscope
149 (Olympus BX51 with a Pixelink M20C-CYL camera) and a Neubauer chamber (Carl
150 Roth GmbH & Co. KG, Karlsruhe, Germany). Once the cultures reached the
151 stationary phase, they were collected by centrifugation in sterile 50 mL Falcon tubes
152 at $3220 \times g$ for 40 min.

153 Furthermore, a 10 \times concentrated *M. sedula* culture grown on pyrite was recultivated
154 in 50 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with the following mineral materials: two Mars analog
155 materials, JEZ-1 Jezero Delta Simulant (Exolith) and ESA01-E Martian basalt analog,
156 pyrite, rutile, anatase, illmenite, and titanium dioxide, in a shake incubator set at 100
157 rpm and 75°C for 72 h. The harvested material was subsequently transferred in 300
158 μL steps (3 mL in total) to metal exposure wells and air-dried.

159 To track microbial growth, samples from the cultures were collected continuously
160 throughout the growth phase, and cell counts were determined using a microscope
161 (Olympus BX51 with a Pixelink M20C-CYL camera) and a Neubauer chamber (Carl
162 Roth GmbH & Co. KG, Karlsruhe, Germany). Once the cultures reached the
163 stationary phase, they were collected by centrifugation in sterile 50 mL Falcon tubes
164 at $3220 \times g$ for 40 min.

165 *Halobacterium salinarum* DSM 3754 was cultivated aerobically in DSMZ 97 medium²
166 without additional MnSO₄ × H₂O in 50 mL Erlenmeyer flasks in a shake incubator set
167 at 100 rpm and 37°C for 504 h. The cultures were continuously and directly
168 transferred into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes for further experiments. Additionally, a
169 portion of the harvested material was subsequently transferred in 300 µL steps (3 mL
170 in total) to metal exposure wells and air-dried.

171 *Scanning Electron Microscopy*

172 *H. salinarum* cells were cultivated as described above until they reached a high cell
173 density, which was assessed by light microscopy. A 1 mL aliquot of the culture was
174 fixed by adding glutaraldehyde (Sigma-Aldrich) to a final concentration of 2 %. The
175 samples were fixed for 2.5 h at room temperature.

176 After fixation, 100 µL of the cell suspension was applied to a Whatman[®] Nuclepore
177 polycarbonate filter disc (0.2 µm pore size, 13 mm diameter; Cytiva). The filters were
178 washed once with double-distilled water and air-dried at room temperature. The dried
179 filters were mounted onto SEM specimen stubs (12.5 mm diameter, 3.2 × 8 mm pin;
180 Agar Scientific) using double-adhesive tape.

181 The samples were sputter-coated with gold/palladium (Au/Pd) for 10 s at ~20 mA and
182 2.45 kV using a Polaron SEM Coating Unit E5100. Scanning electron microscopy
183 (SEM) was performed using a ZEISS GeminiSEM with an in-lens detector operating
184 at an electron high tension (EHT) of 5 kV.

185 **Glucosidase Experiment**

186 *para*-Nitrophenyl-β-D-glucopyranoside (*p*NPG, CAS RN: 2492-87-7) was purchased
187 from TCI Europe N.V. Its mirror image, *para*-nitrophenyl-β-L-glucopyranoside (*L*-
188 *p*NPG) has never been described, and was prepared following a three-steps
189 synthetic route described for *p*NPG [Riou et al., 1998], starting from L-glucose
190 (Sigma-Aldrich). Its ¹H NMR spectrum was consistent with the literature data for
191 *p*NPG [Riou et al., 1998] and was identical to that of commercial *p*NPG, as expected
192 for enantiomeric compounds. Similarly, reverse-phase HPLC analysis showed an
193 identical retention time for *p*NPG. *L*-*p*NPG: ¹H NMR (600 MHz, methanol-d₄) δ 8.20
194 (d, *J* = 9.3 Hz, 2H), 7.23 (d, *J* = 9.3 Hz, 2H), 5.14 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 3.92 (dd, *J* =
195 12.4, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 3.74 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 5.7 Hz, 1H), 3.64 – 3.54 (m, 2H), 3.47 (dd, *J* =
196 9.3, 9.3 Hz, 1H). **MS** (ESI+): [M+Na]⁺ *m/z* calculated for C₁₂H₁₅NNaO₈: 324.1, found:
197 324.0. **RP-HPLC** (C18 HR chromolith, 100 × 4.6 mm, 3 mL flow rate, solvent A =
198 H₂O/TFA 99.9:0.1, solvent B = MeCN/TFA 99.9:0.1, gradient: 5 to 95 B in 5 min), *t_R* =
199 1.24 min.

² https://www.dsmz.de/microorganisms/medium/pdf/DSMZ_Medium97.pdf

200 β -Glucosidase was extracted from sweet almond seeds. Briefly, almond seeds (10 g)
201 were grounded in 100 mL phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) using a kitchen hand
202 blender. The resulting suspension was filtered through a sintered glass funnel using
203 a sand pad to prevent clogging, centrifuged at 20,000 RPM for 30 min, and finally
204 filtered through a 0.2 μ m membrane to obtain a clear solution, which was stored at 4
205 $^{\circ}$ C.

206 *β -Glucosidase Chromogenic Assays*

207 All experiments were performed in triplicate.

208 *Control experiments with sweet almond β -glucosidase.* Almond seed extract (30 μ L)
209 was diluted in PBS (270 μ L), and 100 μ L of a 20 mM aqueous solution of pNPG or L-
210 pNPG, or water (negative control) was added (final probe concentration: 5 mM). The
211 resulting solution was then incubated at room temperature. The release of para-
212 nitrophenolate was monitored by the experimenter.

213 *β -L/D-glucosidase assays on *Halobacterium salinarum*.* To 300 μ L of *H. salinarum*
214 culture in DSMZ 97 medium, 100 μ L of a 20 mM aqueous solution of either pNPG or
215 L-pNPG or water (final probe concentration: 5 mM) was added, and the resulting
216 suspension was incubated at room temperature. Para-nitrophenolate release was
217 monitored by the experimenter.

218 **Extended Discussion**

219 *Art and Science: Towards a Synthesis*

220 To ensure such interstellar political correctness, we tested whether our microbial
221 astronauts, *M. sedula* and *H. salinarum*, could utilize L-sugars. We chose to design
222 and focus on experiments with *H. salinarum* (**Figure 6**) because of its potential for
223 glycolysis (Baati et al. 2024) and in contrast to *M. sedula*, of the cultivation modalities
224 and the clarity of the cell-medium mixture to clearly observe a potential color
225 activation in the previously described enzymatic hydrolysis of para-nitrophenyl- β -D-
226 glucopyranose (pNPG), resulting in a bright yellow color.

227

228 **Figure 6:** Scanning electron microscopy micrograph of two rod-shaped and salt-encrusted *H.*
229 *salinarum* cells (white circle). Scale bar is 90 nm and is indicated in white on the bottom-right.
230 The analysis was conducted at the Archaea Centre at the University of Regensburg (ZEISS
231 GeminiSEM).

232 *Glucosidase Experiment*

233 *Control experiment with sweet almond β -glucosidase.* As a control experiment, we
234 tested the activity of sweet almond β -glucosidase using both pNPG and L-pNPG
235 probes. Incubation with pNPG rapidly produced a yellow color, reflecting the release
236 of p-nitrophenolate upon enzymatic hydrolysis. The color intensity plateaued within 5
237 min, indicating complete substrate consumption. In contrast, no color change was
238 observed with L-pNPG, even after extended incubation for up to 15 days, indicating
239 the absence of β -L-glucosidase activity.

240 *Cell experiment.* The viability of the microorganisms was validated before starting the
241 experiment. During the incubation assays, no color change was observed in either
242 pNPG- or L-pNPG-treated samples, even after 15 days, suggesting the absence of
243 secreted β -glucosidase activity in *H. salinarum*.

244 Since it was also possible that other enzymes, such as nitroreductases (Akiva et al.
245 2017), could inactivate the chromogenic properties of pNPG and L-pNPG substrates,
246 we added almond β -glucosidase to both samples after 15 days. This treatment led to
247 a rapid color change to bright yellow (reaching a plateau within 5 min) in the pNPG
248 sample, whereas no coloration was detected in the L-pNPG sample. This result
249 confirmed that pNPG and likely also L-pNPG substrates remained intact and that
250 pNPG could still be properly hydrolyzed by β -glucosidase.

251 We also considered the possibility that if present in *H. salinarum*, the β -glucosidase
252 of our microorganism astronaut might not be secreted. To test this hypothesis, we
253 repeated the experiment using lysed cells (cell lysis was performed by ultrasonication
254 in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min) to release intracellular proteins into the solution.
255 However, no reaction was observed over 15 days, and the addition of almond β -
256 glucosidase again produced the same results as above.

257 In conclusion, although our assumption that “native-chirality” β -glucosidases
258 hydrolyze only carbohydrate substrates with the natural L-configuration was
259 consistent with the observations, no such enzymatic activity was detected in the
260 potential microbial astronaut *H. salinarum*, with either the Earth-borne D-glucose
261 substrate or the L-glucose mirror image. This finding suggests that *H. salinarum* could
262 serve as a suitable Earth ambassador, safely carrying either D- or L-chirality
263 carbohydrate analogs to probe extra-terrestrial handedness.

264 Although more difficult to assay, a (commercially available) sweet gift of L-glucose
265 could be considered a “safe” present aboard the starship during the long voyage
266 alongside the *H. salinarum* crew, as it is non-metabolizable by them, while still
267 potentially metabolizable by mirror-image extra-terrestrial organisms.

268 In contrast, D-glucose is likely a less suitable option, although it has not been proven
269 to be metabolized under our experimental conditions. It is conceivable that our
270 microbial astronauts possess or could evolve metabolic pathways that would enable
271 them to utilize it as an energy source.

272 From a practical perspective, the unprecedented β -L-glucosidase chromogenic probe
273 prepared and rigorously characterized in this study, L-pPNPG, could be useful for
274 terrestrial scientists willing to identify and measure β -L-glucosidase activities in
275 terrestrial enzymes yet to be discovered.

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